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The Core Elements in Sustaining Effective Professional Development for Early Childhood Education Teachers

Joyce L. Bautista , Sophia binti Md Yassin*
Universiti Pendidikan Sultan Idris

***Corresponding Author**

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Abstract: The increasing demand for a new culture for quality education implicates a new way of thinking and implementing effective continuing professional development for early childhood education teachers. Early childhood education teachers need to be able to commit themselves to continuing professional development to remain current and to successfully achieve high quality education for all young children and their families. Effective continuing professional development programs help early childhood education teachers grow personally and professionally. The inclusion of the core elements that make continuing professional development effective is more important than the type of activities being considered in most programs. (Desimone, 2009; Desimone, Porter, Garet, Yoon, & Birman, 2002; Garet, Porter, Desimone, Birman, & Yoon, 2001). The core elements provides a framework in sustaining and unifying the vision that will guide the conduct of professional development programs for early childhood education teachers and to make them relevant to the needs of the times. The core elements in sustaining effective professional development should be: 1) assessment-focused; 2) learner-focused; 3) content-focused; and 4) community of practice-focused. School administrators, professional development providers and early childhood education teachers will be on the right path given the right framework with comprehensive outcomes in planning for professional development programs.

Keywords: sustaining effective professional development, core elements for professional development, early childhood education teachers

Introduction

The key educational reform for the 21st century is the building of a new culture for quality education through effective continuous upgrading of teachers' competence and work performance (Schleicher, 2012). Teachers need to fit a specific context which can be achieved by supporting their continuous professional development (CPD). By continuing to develop their competencies after entering the profession, teachers should be able to remain updated with new developments in the field and increase their knowledge about instruction and student learning, both of which support teacher effectiveness (Reutzell & Clark, 2014).

In the face of growing attention to ECE teachers CPD, there is a concomitant need for collaborative efforts to examine what works for whom, within which contexts, and its content (NAEYC, 2009). Researches on ECE teachers' CPD must go beyond basic need for teachers' characteristics and their associations with attributes of knowledge, skill, or practice. Rather, it should establish a scientific way that requires building a body of evidence about not only its forms but also its processes to influence change (Darling-Hammond, 2017). It implies a shift in paradigm on how CPD is conceptualized, organized and delivered to retool and retrofit teachers.

There is an increasing recognition that core elements for CPD are required to address the varying demands and issues in the ECE field (Sheridan, Marvin, & Knoche, 2009). The NAEYC(1993) believes that efforts to promote a high-quality CPD system for ECE teachers' development can be an instrument to successfully achieve high quality education for all young children and their families. This CPD system include the core elements which describe the current diversity of early childhood service providers, preparation opportunities, the analogy to describe the professional knowledge, performances, and dispositions connected with ECE teachers', and elements of CPD opportunities. These elements unify the vision that will guide the development and conduct of PDP in ECE, and to make them relevant to the needs of the times and to respond to quality of expectations of varied sectors.

Professional Development Programs for Teachers

Professional development programs are structured professional learning programs that result in changes in teacher practices and improvements in children's development and learning outcomes (Darling-Hammond, Hyler, & Gardner, 2017). ECE teachers may have varied reasons in attending any formal or informal PDP due to an interest for lifelong learning, to improve professional competence to enhance career progression, to keep abreast to latest educational trends and practices, or to comply with the national professional regulatory requirements in order to maintain professional license to retain employment. Whereas, growing evidence indicates that training alone is insufficient, and that comprehensive system with defined elements are necessary to transfer knowledge, skills, and positive attitude to impact practice, improve program quality, and develop children holistically. McFarland (2014) in his study titled "Teachers' Views of Professional Development: What do Teachers Really Needs That Makes Them Willing to Change Professional Practice?" identified elements of CPD teachers perceive to be most important, and what specific characteristics about CPD influence their willingness to make changes in their professional practices. Data analysis indicated four statistically significant elements: Individual Teacher Needs; Student

and Teacher Learning; Collaboration; Supportive Structures and Environment. Darling-Hammond, et. al (2017) defined features of effective CPD, they reviewed studies meeting the methodological criteria that emerged from extensive search of the literature over the last three decades. Using this methodology, it was found that effective CPD incorporates the following elements: 1) Is content focused; 2) incorporates active learning; 3) supports collaboration; 4) uses models of effective practice; 5) provides coaching and expert support; and 6) offers feedback and reflection; 7) is of sustained duration.

If education is to remain globally competitive in the 21st century, teachers need superior teaching competence (i.e. content and pedagogy) to develop critical thinking skills among children (Wei, Darling-Hammond, Adamson, 2010). Kimble, Yager&Yager, Stuart (2017) state that teachers are the key to any school reform and as such need to be prepared and cultivated throughout their teaching career if they are to effectuate change in the classroom. Therefore, the government, the school should consider PD activities for teachers as the driving force behind change and improvement in the teaching field (Darling-Hammond, et. al., 2017). The ECE teachers are not exempted to this.

Features of Effective Professional Development

Desimone (2011) identified five primary features of effective PD intended to bring about changes in teachers' knowledge and practice. She concluded that, to be effective, CPD should: (a) focus on subject matter content and how children learn it, (b) engage teachers in active learning, (c) be consistent with teachers' knowledge and beliefs and district and state reform policies, (d) last for an extended period of time involving at least twenty contact hours, and (e) involve groups of teachers from the same grade or school. Consistent with Desimone's (2011) elements of effective CPD, found that CPD including active learning with research-based classroom practices and coaching helped support the successful implementation of a CPD program. Active learning should also be considered for it offers opportunities for discussion, planning, and practice based upon what they are learning between and among CPD participants (Hannele, Nevgi, &Askit 2016). Research has also shown that teachers with higher senses of efficacy are more likely to implement what they learn in CPD than teachers with lower senses of efficacy (Sandholtz&Ringstaff, 2013). However, based on (a) PD's prominence in conforming to education standards and policy, (b) its role in helping teachers enhance their knowledge and skills, and (c) the positive impact PD can have on increasing teachers' sense of efficacy for instruction, it is useful to briefly overview elements that contribute to PD's effectiveness (Griffith, Ruan, Stepp, & Kimmel, 2014; Tchannen-Moran & Chen, 2014).

Bridging the span between policy and practice requires that academic leaders engage teachers in PD activities designed to provide specific training related to changes delineated within the details of academic reform (Eilers & D'Amico, 2012). Pitsoe (2012) stressed that effective PD in a constructivist point of view involves teachers both as learners and as teachers and allows them to struggle with the uncertainties that accompany each role. It furthermore displays a number of characteristics: (1) It must engage teachers in concrete tasks of teaching, assessment, observation and reflection, which will illuminate the processes of learning and development. (2) It must be based from inquiry, reflection and experimentation that are participant-driven. (3) It must be collaborative, involving a sharing of knowledge among educators and a focus on teachers' communities of practice, rather than on individual teachers. (4) It must be connected to and derived from teachers' work with their children. (5) It must be sustained, ongoing, intensive and supported by modelling, coaching and the collective solving of specific problems pertaining to practice; and (6) It must be connected to other aspects of school change (Darling-Hammond and McLaughlin, 1995).

Sustaining Effective Professional Development

ECE teachers play an important role in building child's foundation for current and future success. The quality and effectiveness of ECE teachers is one of the most important factors how well children do inside and outside school. They do more than facilitate school activities throughout the day. Minding how each child progresses in all aspects of development is a more than a tough job. According to J. D. Bransford (2010) in Wells (2014), "If teachers are to prepare an ever more diverse group of students, they will need substantially more knowledge and radically different skills than most now have and most schools of education now develop." If there should be a shift in understanding and guiding children's development; the schools' top management should think of how teachers develop and enhance their competencies through PDP.

The Importance of Sustainable Professional Development

A key aim in recent years internationally has been to develop sustainable PD for teachers who engage in developing effective pedagogy (Askew & Burns, 2005; Jaworski, 2006; Muir & Beswick, 2007). According to the findings of the report by Back, De Geest, Hirst, and Joubert (2009), some key indicators of the effectiveness of PD are opportunities to develop networks, a focus on student learning, and the facilitation of reflection on teaching practice. This study considers the essential dimensions and domains of a framework as a vehicle for SPD for ECE teachers. It illustrates how the on-going PD programs develop to support the participants in sustaining their development as expert users of effective pedagogical practices

in teaching children. Teachers development program guideline further targets at sustainable standards of teachers' professional growth through the improvements of teachers quality, assuring teachers' motivation, encouraging action researches and collaborative studies, quality teacher education, continuous in-service short term trainings and experience sharing to add to the overall goal of achieving quality education (Daniel, Desalegn, &Girma (2013). CPD programs also improves teaching skills such as self-evaluation, conducting action research, lesson planning, and successful classroom management using variety of teaching techniques, creating teachers' collaboration in team work exercise continuous assessment practices, and considering gender issues (Harvey, 2015).

Sustaining PD programming over time is an important vehicle for helping teachers to increase their knowledge (Darling-Hammond & Sykes, 1999). They concluded that sustaining PD programming over time and the resulting opportunities for collaboration among teachers were significant factors that led teachers to implement what they learned. Similarly, in their study of teachers' levels of content knowledge and its impact on their ability to select appropriate instructional activities based on children' needs, Carreker, Joshi, and Boulware-Gooden (2010) found teachers' content knowledge and selection of appropriate instructional activities were related to the number of hours of CPD they completed.

Strategies in Sustaining Effective Professional Development Programs

In an article by Singh, Schrape, and Kelly (2012) on Emerging strategies for a sustainable approach to PD disclosed that the term sustainability broadly refers to the capacity to achieve durability in practice. The primary consideration of sustainability is from the perspective of achieving shifts in knowledge, skills and attitudes that contribute to lasting change in technology integrated teaching and learning practices. Additionally, sustainability in terms of approach, address staff needs and institutional priorities in a timely and resource efficient manner. Sustainable professional development (SPD) aims to strengthen links to classroom practices; create on-going, self-directed and collaborative opportunities for teachers to engage in learning and developments; to keep updated on the educational trends; to promote innovative and research-based pedagogies. This aligns sustainability approach to professional development and learning to some of Hawley and Valli (1999) influential design principles. The strategies employed incorporate contemporary elements of PD such as teacher networks, joint networks, collaborations, action research, mentor programs and peer coaching, as we believe these address complex and multifaceted needs, and sustainable practice.

Investing in SPD means connecting to existing competencies to new skills and abilities through effective professional learning programs. In the study of Yaxley (2015) which is focused on investing in SPD exposed that there are practical strategies or CPD activities that support the progressive perspective on SPD for teachers. Some SPD strategies include: 1) Creating a learning culture. This helps attract and retain committed ECE teachers, boost performance, improve problem solving and drive innovation that bridge between current competencies and achieving future potential. 2) Professional Learning Communities strategy. It illustrates how CPD strategies can support teachers to engage in a collaborative network, develop their professional knowledge, and reflect on their teaching practice. 3) Learning and development (L&D) strategy. It involves pro-active management of knowledge, skills and abilities and/or competencies to ensure effective and sustainable performance. 4) Assessment and follow-up. In a study on “Teachers Teaching Teachers: A Sustainable and Inexpensive Professional Development Program to Improve Instruction” by Campbell (2014) revealed that CPDs with no assessment and follow-up as having little or no impact on instructional practices.

Yaxley (2015) suggested six elements that contribute towards effective CPD into personal, functional and organisational planning processes. The elements helps to establish:

Professional development needs of individuals and teams

Review processes that monitor continuous and incremental learning

A pro-active learning culture and community of practice

Identification of available and suitable developmental strategies

Specific learning objectives, responsibilities and expectations

Evidence of performance improvements to support career progression.

The Core Elements of Sustainable Professional Development

With a large and growing body of evidence that the inclusion of the core elements that make CPD programs effective is more important than the type of activity (Desimone, 2009; Desimone, Porter, Garet, Yoon, & Birman, 2002; Garet, Porter, Desimone, Birman, & Yoon, 2001), it is essential that CPD using these core elements as a framework and then reflect on their practice via feedback from participants to ensure continual improvement.

Figure 1 shows the most recognized core elements for CPD to create a path for professional growth and development of ECE teachers. The core elements include: 1) learner-focused to addresses the diverse needs of the diverse population of ECE teachers by making it accessible to all; 2) content-focused to address the multiple areas of development through timely research-based educational updates aligned with the core competencies, core values, core

standards, domains, and resources of the ECE curriculum; 3) community of practice-focused where teachers are involved in the planning of their CPD programs and where administrators monitor and supervise teaching performance that integrate learned content and pedagogy from the CPD program; 4) assessment of teachers which provides for a focused and principled guide to CPD development with particular considerations to the giving of feedback which offers opportunities for the reflection of teaching practice. The arrows point to the ongoing process of PD to sustain ECE teachers knowledge and skills they need to deliver a professional service to the children, school, and community.

Fig.1. The Core Elements of SPD

A. Assessment-Focused

Conducting assessments and surveys regularly will help administrators and PD providers with better understanding of teachers' needs. However, teachers should also be responsible of their own learning. This will allow them to create needs-driven programming helping them to stay engaged in their professional development long-term. The provision and receipt of feedback is essential to education sphere. Through administrator feedback, peer feedback, and self-feedback (reflection), ECE teachers learn about both the art and science of teaching. There is also a need include assessment of children's performance and development which provides direct feedback on how well the teachers benefited from the PDPs they attended. SPD provides built-in time for teachers to think about, receive input on, and revise their practice by facilitating reflection and soliciting feedback that will help asses' attainment of

goal. Feedback and reflection both help teachers to thoughtfully move toward the expert visions of practice.

Assessment-focused SPD will contribute to achieving the following outcomes:

- Delivery incorporates components of collaborative discussion around children's work, development, and assessments.
- Delivery responds to prior feedback from teachers and adapts to meet identified teacher learning needs.
- Delivery always includes an evaluation/ feedback component that includes ECE teachers-participant impact measures.
- PDP is evaluated in terms of impact on classroom and feedback is given to improve the PD of ECE teachers.
- The evaluation plan uses a wide variety of strategies, modalities, and tools to gather information from all participants.
- Feedback mechanisms are in place and encouraged, so that adjustments can be made on a continuous basis to PDP.

B. Learners-Focused

ECE teachers are professional learners whose background, needs, interest, experiences, dispositions, and diversity should be considered in designing and implementing PD programs. ECE teachers are examples of how learning works. They inquire, explore, examine process, consider, and reflect. Through SPD programs, ECE teachers are given opportunities to nurture the skills, dispositions, and knowledge. Faced with new policies, standards and curriculum, ECE teachers and global educational demands need to know it is practical and useful to participate in SPD programs. Hence, ECE teachers should be provided with technical, emotional, and even financial support for the pursuit of successful learning and teaching.

Learner-focused SPD will contribute to achieving the following outcomes:

- PD initiatives address the needs, interest, and career stage of ECE teachers.
- Critical information from PD providers are considered.
- Delivery models fully engage teachers as active learners, inquirers, and problem-solvers.
- Modifications of PD plans are developed in response to ECE teachers' comments, evaluation data and impact.

C. Content-Focused

SPD programs that focus on teaching strategies associated with specific curriculum content supports teacher learning within ECE classroom contexts. SPD program is a multifaceted system to learning since it relates not only to the specific content or skills of the curriculum but also to teaching strategies, different types of learner intelligences, and even interpersonal and intrapersonal skills. The teacher who is equipped with a wide understanding of the curriculum being taught can create an environment that truly supports every child in their quest to learning and optimum development. Effective SPD experiences enhance teachers' content knowledge and content pedagogy within the framework of a teacher's vision for his or her classroom. However, it will only be possible if active learning, flexible learning, and sound implementation of the CPD programs of ECE teachers will be considered.

Content-focused SPD will contribute to achieving the following outcomes:

- A continuous process of collecting and analyzing data from PD program evaluation is evident.
- Plans, strategies and decisions about professional development are based on the analysis of data from the ECE teachers-participants.
- Research-based PD program is evident in the planning process
- Delivery modes are built upon what the ECE teachers already know and able to do support of their career stages.
- Delivery content focuses on teaching effective content and pedagogy to meet the learning needs of all children and the ECE teachers.
- Delivery incorporates some opportunities to practice inquiry, engaging ECE teachers as active learners, inquirers, and problem solvers.
- Delivery is predominantly facilitative and proactive.

- Parents and community members are provided opportunities to plan and participate in professional development initiatives and to serve on a wide variety of school committees.
- School stakeholders participate in the professional development programs.
- The school reports to the community organizations and other school stakeholders about the professional development activities.
- School stakeholders provide input from a personal perspective.

D. Community of Practice-Focused

When teachers have opportunities to learn with and from one another, a culture of collaboration and possibilities can emerge that often does not otherwise. SPDP provide opportunities for professional learning community (PLC) (such as School Learning Action Cell (SLAC), District-wide, Division-wide, and Region-wide) where ECE teachers collaborate with their colleagues and receive on-going support from their administration and trainers or mentors, and PD providers. Communities of practice help to decentralize knowledge and expertise, allowing the teachers to take more agency in their professional development. This increases the likelihood of teachers incorporating feedback and changing their practices.

Community of practice-focused SPD will contribute to achieving the following outcomes:

- Administrators insure equal and equitable professional development opportunities for all ECE teachers.
- There is regular and on-going dissemination of information of PD opportunities through a wide variety of formal and informal communication techniques, i.e., newsletters, meetings, daily discussions and conversations among staff, online networks.
- Administrators serve as instructional leaders and participate in professional development activities.
- Administrators work collaboratively with the ECE teachers, school staff and community with evidence of mutual respect in designing, organizing, implementing, and evaluating School, District, Division, and Regional PDPs.
- Administrators allocate and direct resources to support professional development activities to ensure meeting the needs of all teachers, children, and staff.
- System supports provide teachers regular opportunities to collaborate with peers, including co-observations of teaching, team teaching, modeling and feedback, and mentoring.
- Lecturers of presenters are respectful of, and responsive to, ECE teachers' learning needs.
- At least annually, a formal presentation is made to the community on the overall status of PD of the ECE teachers.

Conclusion:

The kind of nurturing one receives during early childhood stage has a profound impact on their current and later life. Each child has their own personality, strength, and intrinsic talent that need to be supported and developed by the people who have a genuine love and care for them. Parents are not alone in fulfilling this task in the form of ECE teachers. However, ECE teachers need to be able to commit themselves to SPD to remain current and to effectively do their job. The aforementioned core elements are pivotal in providing a framework for effective SPD for ECE teachers. Education leaders and PD providers must be mindful in planning, evaluating, and selecting PDPs based on the core elements. ECE teachers will be on the right path given the right frame on PDPs. If we want our ECE teachers to help our children develop and succeed, we need to support the ECE teachers how to effectively do it.

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